

Predicting Intracellular Calcium Effects through Hair Bundle Dynamic Modeling

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Abstract. We have developed a model of an isolated outer hair cell (OHC) hair bundle (HB) to mechanistically analyze its behavior under various experimental conditions. We incorporated nonlinear kinematics, viscoelastic kinetics, and motor-based adaptation mechanisms. We applied this model to assess the impact of intracellular calcium concentrations on HB displacements and mechano-electric transducer (MET) currents, comparing results from normal and low calcium environments. After calibrating the model with normal calcium data, we primarily adjusted motor parameters and pivot stiffness to fit the low calcium data. We quantitatively replicated the experimental HB creep and current adaptation, including a decrease in the adaptation magnitude, an increase in the resting open probability, and a leftward shift in the activation curve upon calcium reduction. Finally, we use the two calcium models to show that a “motor” model can predict the non-correlation between the creep and slow current adaptation.

INTRODUCTION

HBs protruding from apices of cochlear mechanoreceptors (OHCs and inner hair cells) transduce mechanical stimuli to electrical signals. They consist of 50-100 stereocilia arranged in three rows of varying heights, typically in a V or W shape in OHCs [1]. The tallest stereocilia, embedded in the tectorial membrane (TM), respond to external stimuli, mobilizing the shorter rows via protein linkages called tip links and top connectors. This movement induces tension in tip links, altering the lipid bilayer near the lower tip link density (LTLD), the attachment of tip link to shorter stereocilia, to open mechano-electric transducer (MET) channels, allowing cation influx [2]. This influx generates an MET current that depolarizes the OHC and facilitates amplification. Under step-like stimulation, HB displacement exhibits mechanical creep (slow increase) and the MET current displays biphasic adaptation (decay): fast adaptation within 0.3-5 ms and slow adaptation exceeding 10 ms [3]. Fast adaptation is typically linked to cation-protein interactions within the MET channel [4], while slow adaptation may involve myosin slipping at the upper tip link density (UTLD), the attachment of tip link to taller stereocilia [5, 6]. The mechanisms underlying adaptation and the role of cations in this process remain incompletely understood. Given that adaptation may be crucial for precluding tip link damage caused by excessive mechanical loading, it is imperative to investigate its origins further.

Researchers use various experimental techniques to identify MET channel components and their effects on adaptation, as detailed in [7]. To interpret these findings mechanistically, mathematical models of HBs have been developed, evolving in complexity alongside our understanding of MET channel constituents. Early models represented the MET channel as a mechanically gated ion channel with a gating spring [8]. Later models incorporated a “motor” component to explain slow adaptation [5, 6], while more advanced models with additional degrees of freedom addressed fast adaptation [4, 9]. Tinevez *et al.* [10] proposed a two-row dynamic model with instantaneous feedback from cations, but it failed to capture simultaneous creep and fast adaptation observed in mammals. Nam *et al.* [11] developed a comprehensive model with 29 columns, emphasizing the need for three rows to accurately represent biphasic adaptation, though it requires approximately ~6300 degrees of freedom and extensive computational resources.

To address these issues, we developed a simplified three-stereocilia-row model of an isolated HB that accurately represents the bundle biophysics. Our model integrates nonlinear kinematics, viscoelastic kinetics, and conceptualized adaptation as the slip or climb of the UTLD. We utilized this model to fit experimental responses from Caprara *et al.* [12] under both normal and low intracellular calcium concentrations. These fits provide insights into HB behavior under varying calcium levels from a mechanical perspective. Additionally, we investigated whether a motor-based model could predict the experimentally observed non-correlation between creep and slow adaptation [12] using models for normal and low calcium concentrations.

MODEL AND METHODS

Our three-stereocilia-row model is illustrated in Fig. 1, where a single column approximates the multi-column bundle response. The essential viscoelastic elements are defined in Fig. 1A and the geometric parameters are described in Fig. 1B. Two adjacent stereocilia are linked via a tip link equipped with a gating-spring mechanism [8] at the LTLD, as shown in Fig. 1C (top). They also share a sliding contact constraint. The UTLD is equipped with an adaptation mechanism that actively modulates the extent of its slip or climb through a spring-damper system. We assume that

FIGURE 1. Schematic of the three-row model. (A) Staircase arrangement of the bundle with viscoelastic components: gating springs $K_{GS_j} = 85.3$ (82.7) mN/m, pivot springs $K_{SP_i} = 30$ (6) fN.m/rad, extent springs $K_{ES_j} = 45$ (105) mN/m, extracellular damping $\lambda_i = 25.8$ aN.m.s/rad, and intracellular damping $\lambda_{aj} = 1.1$ (1.4) mN.s/m for $i \in [1, 3]$ and $j \in [1, 2]$. The values within parentheses are for the low concentration model, if altered. The three degrees-of-freedom are ϕ , l_{a1} , and l_{a2} for bundle rotation, and displacements of two adaptation motors, respectively. (B) Geometric definitions when $\phi = 0$. Geometric parameters are: $r_1 = r_2 = 113$ nm, $r_3 = 82.45$ nm, $r_{CA} = 4.2$ μ m, row 2 length is $r_{BD} + r_2 = 2.2$ μ m, row 3 length is $r_{EF} + r_3 = 1.1$ μ m, $b_{12} = b_{23} = 0.61$ μ m, $l_1^{gs} = 2.3$ μ m, and $l_2^{gs} = 1$ μ m [9]. (C) Gating mechanism (top) and cation feedback mechanism in row 2 (bottom) defined by parameters that include gating swing $d_j = 3.2$ nm, transduction channels in each row-pair $N = 120$, resting gating-spring extension $l_j^{act} = 41.1$ (20.5) pm, and calcium feedback terms- motor stall force $F_{max_j} = 30$ (150) pN and strength $S = 0.8$ (0). The adjusted parameter values for the low concentration model are indicated in parentheses.

the slow adaptation may be affected by calcium entry, making middle row the only plausible location for such a mechanism to occur due to the relative proximity of its UTLD to the MET channel (shown in Fig. 1C at the bottom). The bundle rotation (ϕ) and the displacements of the two adaptation motors (l_{a1} and l_{a2}), shown in Fig. 1A, govern bundle dynamics. A two-state Boltzmann relation, function of the difference between open and closed channel states, governed by gating-spring extension (δl_j), defines the channel open probability at each LTLD, as shown in Eq (1).

$$P_{oj} = \{1 + \exp[-K_{GS_j} d_j (\delta l_j - l_j^{act}) / N k_B T]\}^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

where the parameter definitions can be found in Fig. 1 description. $j = 1$ and $j = 2$ correspond to LTLD of rows 2 and 3, respectively. We then derive the three coupled dynamic equations that have the form shown in Eqs (2)-(4).

$$\dot{\phi}(t) = f(t, \phi, l_{a1}, l_{a2}), \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{l}_{a1}(t) = g(t, \phi, l_{a1}, l_{a2}), \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{l}_{a2}(t) = m(t, \phi, l_{a1}, l_{a2}), \quad (4)$$

where f , g , and m are nonlinear functions of the three degrees of freedom and time t obtained using Lagrangian formulation. Finally, we define the model outputs: HB displacement as $X_{hb} = r_{CA} \sin(\phi)$ and MET current as $I_{met} = G_{max}(\Delta V_{hb}^o - EP)(P_{o1} + P_{o2})$, where $G_{max} = 5.2$ nS is the maximum channel conductance of each row pair, $\Delta V_{hb}^o = -80$ mV is the OHC holding potential, and $EP = 0$ mV is the endocochlear potential.

We used MATLAB to define the kinematics and a custom-written 4th-order Runge-Kutta method to numerically solve for the outputs in time-domain. The tallest row was stimulated with a step-like force resembling the experimental fluid-jet force with a typical rise-time of 0.1 ms [12]. We conducted parametric studies, employing sensitivity analysis and error minimization techniques to determine model parameters. In the experiments [12], normal and low calcium concentrations correspond to 0.1 mM and 10 mM intracellular BAPTA, respectively, at a holding potential of -80 mV. For each concentration, we obtain a unique set of parameters that replicates corresponding experiments.

RESULTS

Quantitative Predictions of HB Response in Varied Calcium Concentrations

The HB displacements for the normal and low calcium concentrations are shown in Fig. 2A and 2B, respectively. We note that one set of model parameters quantitatively fits all thirteen experiments in Fig. 2A and a second set of parameters fits all experiments in Fig. 2B, both effectively showing the activation and creep. The normal and low concentration model parameters are given in Fig. 1 caption, where values within parentheses correspond to the low concentration model. Each experiment corresponds to a different externally applied fluid-jet stimulus-level, that we adjust by changing the amplitude of F_{ext} in the model (see Fig. 1A). The corresponding MET currents shown in Figs. 2C and 2D illustrate the efficacy of our model in predicting fast and slow adaptation dynamics observed experimentally. For higher stimulus levels, the predicted MET current saturated earlier than in experiments likely due to our assumption of estimating bundle response from a single column.

FIGURE 2. Quantitative prediction of the bundle responses. Panels (A) and (B) depict HB displacements for normal and low calcium concentrations, respectively, each corresponding to distinct external force levels. Panels (C) and (D) illustrate corresponding MET currents. In panels (A) and (B), mechanical creep is seen following activation, while in panels (C) and (D), MET current adaptation is observed after the peak, albeit diminished in (D). The resting MET current indicates increased resting open probability with decreased calcium. (E) Leftward shift in the activation curve due to decreasing intracellular calcium concentration. These activation curves were constructed using peak currents and corresponding HB displacements. (F) Mechanical creep is defined as the ratio of depicted points 1 and 2. (G) Adaptation magnitude is defined as the ratio of peak and adapted values.

Theoretical Activation Curve Shift Consistent with Experimental Data

We observed a leftward shift of 22 nm in the activation curve, compared to an experimental shift of 24 nm upon calcium reduction, as shown in Fig. 2E. In the low calcium model, we increased K_{ES_j} by 133%, F_{max_j} by 400%, and λ_{a_j} by 28%. Mechanistically, increasing stiffness reduces channel reclosure by decreasing motor response. A higher stall force reduces the effective force on the adaptation complex, pulling the UTLD up and pre-stressing the gating spring, resulting in increased resting open probability. For quantitative fits in Figs. 2A-D, we also decreased I_j^{act} by 50%, K_{SP_i} by 80%, and K_{GS_j} by 3% (see Fig. 1 description for parameter values in the two models). While BAPTA's interaction with tip links [9] likely justifies the small change in K_{GS_j} , its effects on the proteins constituting rootlet stiffness K_{SP_i} are unknown. Moreover, two different experimental cell preparations increase the likelihood of variability in their mechanical properties. Further, the model underestimated the sensitivity by $\sim 19\%$, likely due to the single column bundle approximation and/or simplification of more complex LTLD mechanisms at play. As more details of the MET complex unfold, refinements to the LTLD model may improve these findings.

“Motor” Model Predicts the Non-Correlation Between Creep and Slow Adaptation

Caprara *et al.* [12] argued that the causal link posited between mechanical creep and slow adaptation, forming the basis of “motor” models, is invalidated due to the absence of transduction channels at the UTLD and experimentally observed non-correlation between the two quantities. We examined this non-correlation using our motor-based model. Consistent with experiments, we fitted the mechanical creep with a double exponential and adaptation with a single exponential obtaining their magnitudes as quantified in Fig. 2F and 2G, respectively. We observed nearly constant average mechanical creep (0.2 in normal vs. 0.21 in low calcium), while average adaptation magnitude decreased from 1.16 to 0.99 in low calcium, mirroring experimental findings and suggesting they are not correlated.

CONCLUSION

We saw that our model accurately replicated the experimental decrease in adaptation magnitude, increase in resting open probability, and the leftward shift in activation curve upon intracellular calcium reduction. For physiological force levels experienced by a HB, our model’s predictions are quantitatively reliable, with discrepancies at higher levels arising likely due to use of one HB column. In transitioning from normal to low concentration model, we adjusted adaptation motor parameters (K_{ES_j} , λ_{a_j} , and F_{max_j}) and reduced K_{SP_i} . The notable decrease in K_{SP_i} potentially reflects the unknown behavior of rootlet stiffness under BAPTA influence and differences in experimental cell preparations.

Our investigation into the relationship between mechanical creep and slow adaptation concluded that a motor-based model can predict their non-correlation. The inclusion of a calcium-mediated adaptation complex in the middle row and the presence of three rows in the model may explain this observed non-correlation, warranting further investigation. We plan to explore mechanisms responsible for this non-correlation through fitting same cell responses under both positive (+80 mV) and negative (-80 mV) holding potentials from [12].

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Online Forum]

[Julius Kraut]: What is the solve time of this model?

[Varun Goyal]: The simulations modeled 13 distinct experiments, each predicting hair bundle responses over 160 ms with a time step of $1 \mu\text{s}$, using the Parallel Computing Toolbox. Leveraging parallel computing, the simulations were completed in approximately 2 seconds on the Great Lakes High Performance Computing (HPC) cluster with 30 workers and about 20 seconds on a MacBook Pro (M1 processor, 16 GB RAM) with 8 workers, excluding Parallel Computing Toolbox initialization time. This translates to a simulation time of approximately 0.5 ms per millisecond of bundle response on the HPC cluster and 10 ms per millisecond on the local system.

[Julius Kraut]: Was the whole model solved in MATLAB and do you think that it can be plugged into other models, for example of an OHC or an entire cochlear model?

[Varun Goyal]: The model is implemented in MATLAB and can be integrated into OHC or global cochlear models. Additionally, we have developed simplified versions of the model, including one with geometric linearization and another with complete linearization. For small bundle displacements, any of these three models can be utilized within existing OHC or global cochlear models, depending on the required level of nonlinearity.

[Julius Kraut]: Did you ever run a frequency study to see how hair bundle displacement and MET current behave for sinusoidal stimuli?

[Varun Goyal]: Not yet, but one of our future objectives is to perform both time-domain and frequency-domain analyses with our three-row model under sinusoidal force excitation. This approach could provide deeper insights into the significance of having exactly three rows of stereocilia and the tonotopic variations in OHC amplification.

[Rayan Chatterjee]: I presume that Figs. 2A and 2B respectively show the displacements relative to the resting displacement of the bundle at high and low calcium. We expect the resting displacements to change between high and low calcium because the mechanical properties of the bundle change. Do you account for that in your model?

[Varun Goyal]: That is correct. The resting bundle position does change, with a more noticeable alteration in the resting current when comparing Fig. 2C and Fig. 2D for normal and low calcium concentrations, respectively. The caption of Fig. 1 details the bundle properties for normal calcium concentration model, followed by parameters for low calcium concentration model in parentheses. These changes in bundle properties result in different resting bundle positions and resting open probabilities, consequently affecting the resting current.